

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING GAMES IN TEACHING GRAMMAR TO
YOUNG LEARNERS.

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Abstract: In recent years, the attention to learning and teaching foreign languages is increasing significantly. This requires making foreign language lessons, especially English, interesting, that is, using various innovative methods, technical tools, interactive games that attract different students. The use of such games during the lesson increases the student's enthusiasm for learning science. This article provides information about the effectiveness of using games in teaching grammar to young students.

Key words: foreign language, interactive games, technical tools, didactic games, style of role-playing games, playful grammar.

The fact that learning foreign languages is gaining importance today therefore, languages are taught not only in higher education institutions, schools, but also it is also taught in pre-school educational institutions. Unique in lessons if it is not taught with interesting methods, it is difficult to attract students to the lesson can become a complex task . If you use traditional methods in classes.If it is done in an interesting way, it not only ensures the quality of the lesson, but at the same time prevents boredom and attracts passive students to participate in the lesson. That's it is worth mentioning that when teaching children language, it is necessary to learn from such games, let all students participate equally in it and get news from the lesson (for example, new vocabulary can be memorized, if this process is repeated every day, the student's vocabulary increases to a higher level). A lesson for students it is inappropriate to start with grammatical concepts, especially for students of lower grades it causes boredom quickly. As a result, interest in education may fade .Even the process of greeting with them should be started in an unconventional way, for example, an English song about a kind of greeting to the class when the teacher enters method to start with is an effective method. If the lesson continues in this way, the students are alone during the lesson they do not lose their attention to the task. They even teach English they will wait eagerly. Of course, all this is done by the teacher must organize and it is the pedagogue's responsibility. So a foreign language Some types of games can be mentioned to make learning interesting

What is common in all these descriptions is the fact that games involve many factors such as employing rules, fostering cooperation while making learning fun. One

can simply say that games are enjoyable. However, in addition to being enjoyable, games refer to rules to be followed pointing at a serious instructional planning and delivery process. As expressed by Lee games have a very clear beginning and ending and they are governed by rules. Competition, which is associated with games, plays a crucial role as for the nature of games requires. Learners are excited by competition because the question of who will win or lose remains unanswered until the game is over. Similarly, games' making learning easier in an enjoyable way suggests that games are full of fun which leads to successful learning. In many games, learners are required to cooperate to achieve the goal and most learners enjoy cooperation and social interaction. It is believed that when cooperation and interaction are combined with fun, successful learning becomes more possible. To conclude, no matter how differently games are described, one cannot underestimate their pedagogical value both in teaching and learning a foreign language.

As we know grammar of a language is its foundation. It is very difficult to imagine mastering a language perfectly well without knowing its grammar. Although some communicative methods deny this opinion, it is true. Most learners consider grammar to be dry and dull, learning it boring as well. For me as a teacher, grammar class is always an opportunity for fun. I cannot imagine dry and dull ESL/EFL grammar classes. During class time there are, of course, periods of focused concentration, especially during the first phases of a new unit when the students are trying to grasp an initial understanding of the form and meaning of a structure. We, as teachers, should know that even during those phases, explanations and examples can be enlivened by funny sentences using the students' names or by fun demonstrations or pantomimes. Fun and humor are essential in ESL/EFL classrooms. Interaction and group participation engage students and make information more memorable and relevant. In my experience, many people approach grammar far too seriously, with long, unsmiling faces, in plodding academic style. I think that grammar should not be approached in this way. A teacher can make grammar fun through different games and activities. Games and fun activities for teaching grammar can have purpose if used correctly and at the right time. Such games and activities have a lot of advantages: they can shake things up, help students develop a competitive position, enable to organize team work, get students' stored energy out . If language learners can make use of grammar and apply it in a fun way, they have a better chance to remember it all. They'll be able to practice and master grammar phenomena extensively rather than just learning a good deal of rules superficially.

Activities and games for learning English grammar don't only motivate, but they also generate the idea of competition in the EFL classroom. As it is known, a bit of healthy rivalry never hurts anyone. Students try to do their best when thrown into action, and they'll strive to outmarch their peers and take precedence of their own expectations . We have just said that games and activities help students be competitive, so how can they assist with cooperation? They create interaction between students and between students and a teacher. Students try to support their groupmates and encourage them when competing in teams or pairs. While inculcating this way of teaching grammar students combine their force so as to succeed! Proceeding from these facts, we can say that participating in such games students can not only learn grammar, but they also will get to know the ways of getting to the top of the tree. It's very important to determine the aim of a grammar game in a EFL lesson. Games should not be just other time fillers, or they should not only be funny and entertaining for your learners, but they must also have educational effect.

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